

OPTIMIZATION OF COMPOSITE WING USING GENETIC ALGORITHM

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ABSTRACT

Stacking sequence and their corresponding ply thicknesses plays an important role to fine-tune the strength properties of laminated composites. By optimizing the thicknesses and stacking sequence, the strength properties of a laminate can be greatly improved. Traditional optimization methods can only minimize structural weight based on static analysis. However, in modern aircraft design, aeroelastic constraints are also crucial. Thus, a method considering aeroelastic constraints, strength and stability constraints is developed in this study to optimize a composite wing. Furthermore, it is shown how the method can be applied to discrete optimization problems.

In order to optimize the mass and the strength of the structure, an FEM model is constructed for a composite wing. The solution proceeds using a two-step optimization strategy which is optimizing the thickness of the layer first and then optimizing the stacking sequences. With constraints of flutter speed, maximum displacement, and structure stability, Genetic Algorithms are used to optimize the structure's mass while changes in the thickness and orientation of the layers in the composite laminates of the wing. FEM based optimization model is built using commercial Finite Element software ABAQUS, NASTRAN and optimization platform modeFRONTIER. Static analysis is carried out in ABAQUS, flutter speed is simulated in NASTRAN, and structural stability is checked by empirical formulas. Entire optimization is carried out in modeFRONTIER.

Finally, optimized variable thickness and variable orientation of composite laminates are obtained. Initial results show that weight of composite wing can be reduced by 28.8%, which is of great significance in aircraft design.

1 INTRODUCTION

Advanced composites are widely used in various industrial sectors because of its advantages, such as high specific strength, high specific stiffness, good fatigue resistance, good corrosion resistance etc. Properties of composites can be greatly improved by adjusting layers' thickness and stacking sequences. Thus, optimization of composite structures to enhance their strength to mass ratio has been an important issue in the aircraft industry.

Optimization methods of composite structures have been studied previously. Riche¹⁰ and Haftka¹⁰ optimized composite laminates' ply sequences and analyzed effects of different genetic factors on structures. Sardinias¹⁵ et al. developed a global multi-starting point optimization method and optimized composite sandwich panels' thickness and angle.

Under the condition of given geometrical constraints of a composite wing, this paper proposed an

initial structural layout scheme and optimized composite wing's ply thickness, ply ratio and ply sequences in order to explore full composite wing structures' ply optimization method.

2 BASELINE FINITE ELEMENT MODEL AND AEROELASTIC MODEL

A baseline finite element model of the composite wing was created using shell elements available in FE software ABAQUS. The wing model has a root chord of 3.8m and a tip chord of 1.2m with a wing span of 50 m. The root section is fully constrained in all DOFs, as shown in Figure 1. The properties of composite material used are defined in Table 1.

Figure 1: Finite element model and wing partition

Engineering constant		Identification
E_{11}	[GPa]	154
E_{22}	[GPa]	9.4
ν_{12}	–	0.302
G_{12}	[GPa]	5.4
G_{23}	[GPa]	3.3

Table 1: Properties of composite

To simplify the complex structure of the wing model it is divided into 29 areas in order to get the convergence. The upper and lower airfoils are divided into 12 areas, whereas ribs and spars are divided into 3 and 2 areas respectively, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 2: Aeroelastic Model

The aeroelastic model is shown in figure 2, which is divided into 2 areas. The static analysis gave a maximum displacement at the wing tip of 3.585m, the twist angle of wing tip is 1.603° and maximum tensile strain, compression strain and shear strain are $4427\mu\epsilon$, $2231\mu\epsilon$ and $7445\mu\epsilon$ respectively. All these three strain value are lower than the allowable strain. The stability of the wing is checked using engineering algorithm and the value of bulking force is lower than maximum critical value. The flutter speed was calculated using P-K method in NASTRAN. The normal modes frequencies are shown in Table 2 and dependent relationship of V-g and V-f is shown in Figure 3. As it can be seen from the

Figure 3, the flutter speed is 110m/s, which is higher than minimum limit of 39m/s and makes the wing safer to fly.

Mode	1	2	3	4	5
Freq(Hz)	1.19	3.43	5.73	6.47	9.06

Table 2: normal modes frequencies of baseline model

Figure 3: Dependent relationship of V-g and V-f

3 EVOLUTIONARY ALGORITHMS

There are two main categories of optimization methods. The first is based on hill-climbing approaches that require gradients to be calculated whereas the second is based on mimicking some form of biological or physical behavior. In this paper, we will only consider the latter type of method. One advantage of the biologically inspired optimization methods is that they can deal easily with discontinuous functions and cannot get stuck at a local optimum point; however, there is no guarantee that the optimum solution is found. There is a wide range of possible evolutionary methods available; Continuous and Binary Genetic Algorithms, Particle Swarm and Ant Colony Optimization. In this study, a Binary Genetic Algorithm was implemented.

3.1 Binary Genetic Algorithms

Genetic Algorithms (GA) are based on the ‘survival of the fittest’ Darwinian Theory of Natural Selection. Starting with an initial random pool’ of genes, different solutions are investigated via a directed random search and the best solutions are carried forward to the next iteration. A key element in setting up a GA optimization is the representation of the problem as a sequence of cells in each gene. In this work, the genes were assigned using the classical binary representation. The creation of new solutions at each iteration (generation) is based on the following operations:

- Crossover. A section of a pair of genes is swapped

$$\begin{array}{c|c} 0\ 1\ 1\ 0 & 1\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 1 \\ \hline 0\ 0\ 1\ 1 & 0\ 1\ 0\ 0\ 0 \end{array} \Rightarrow \begin{array}{c|c} 0\ 1\ 1\ 0 & 0\ 1\ 0\ 0\ 0 \\ \hline 0\ 0\ 1\ 1 & 1\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 1 \end{array}$$

- Mutation. The value of a cell within a gene is randomly swapped

$$0\ 1\ 1\ 0 \textcircled{0} 1\ 0\ 0\ 0 \Rightarrow 0\ 1\ 1\ 0 \textcircled{1} 1\ 0\ 0\ 0$$

- Translation. The order within the gene is randomly swapped

$$0\ 1\ 1\ 0\ 0\ 1\ 0\ 0 | 0\ 0 \Rightarrow 0\ 0 | 0\ 1\ 1\ 0\ 0\ 1\ 0\ 0$$

- New Blood. At each iteration, a number of genes are created independently from the currently utilized genes.

The best genes at each iteration are automatically carried forward into the next generation. The length of each gene is dictated by the expected range of values of the solution and also the number of variables that need to be considered.

3.2 Optimization Parameters

For this exercise, the structural dimensions are left unaltered from the baseline model. The optimization variable is the ply thickness and ply angle across all the different elements of the FE model. Each element of the optimization is assumed to be composed of seven layers, which is $[45/0/-45/\overline{90}]_s$.

The wing was divided into 29 sections based on the optimization variables. The optimization parameters are fixed to 10 iterations. The probability of mutation, crossover and translation are fixed to 1.0, 0.9 and 0.1 respectively.

4 OPTIMIZATION OBJECTIVES

The layers' thicknesses and angles are divided into two-step optimization. Initially, the layers' angles of each area were set to $[45/0/-45/\overline{90}]_s$. using the concept of super ply to optimize each layer's thickness. Secondly, optimizing each area's layers' angles according to the result of the last step. The first optimization was run to achieve the minimum weight and the second was run to achieve maximum stability margin.

4.1 Optimization of layers' thicknesses

In this step of optimization, 36 variables were set to optimize layer's thickness. Each area has 4 variables, t_{45} , t_0 , t_{-45} , t_{90} represent layers' thicknesses of four angles.

$$L_{ij}, i=0, 1, 2, 3; j=0, 1, 2, \dots, 28 \quad (1)$$

Where i represents the value of thickness and 0 to 3, respectively corresponding to 0.125, 0.250, 0.375, 0.500, j represents the number of areas.

4 kinds of constraints were set to limit optimization, including constraint of maximum strain, stability and displacement of the wing tip. The specific values are shown in Table 3.

Type		Value
ensile strain	$[\mu\epsilon]$	<5500
Compression strain	$[\mu\epsilon]$	<4000
Shear strain	$[\mu\epsilon]$	<7600
Stability margin	-	>0
Displacement of wing tip	$[\text{mm}]$	<3900
Flutter speed	$[\text{m/s}]$	<93

Table 3: The specific values of constraints

The optimization was carried out to achieve the minimum weight, which is defined as $\min(w)$.

4.2 Optimization of layers' angle

In this step of optimization, the layer angles are optimized for the 2 sections in the wing root. On the basis of the optimized thicknesses attained from the last step, 9 variables were set to optimize layer's angle in this step of optimization.

$$A_{ij}, i=0, 1, 2, 3; j=0, 1. \quad (2)$$

Where i represents the angle of layers and 0 to 3, respectively, corresponding to 0° , -45° , 45° , 90° , j represents the number of areas.

Constricts are the same as in the last step except for stability margin. This step of optimization is carried out to achieve maximum stability margin.

5 RESULTS

The thickness and angle optimization history is shown in figure 4(a) and figure 4(b), respectively. As can be seen from the figure 4(a), thickness optimization achieves global convergence and optimization reached an optimal value in the tenth iteration. The weight of the wing was reduced from 647.9kg to 461.6kg, which is less than the initial weight of 28.8%. In figure 4(b), the angle optimization achieves local convergence and the value of stability margin was improved from 0.159 to 0.455.

(a) Thickness optimization history

(b) angle optimization history

Figure 4: Thickness and angle optimization history

6 CONCLUSION

In this paper, it has been shown how it is possible to optimize composite structure's layers' thickness and angle with static and aeroelastic constraints using a genetic algorithm. Furthermore, it is shown how the method can be applied to discrete optimization problems. Considerable improvement has been made on reducing the weight of the wing and increasing composite structure's stability margin.

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